

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES AND FIGURES:

Comparative analysis of Annexin A1 (ANXA1) protein expression in 20 different types of cancer.

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Supplementary Table 1: Number of patients, number of tissue samples, and Q-score (average and standard deviation analyzed for 20 types of cancerous samples).

SAMPLE	NUM SAMPLE	NUM PATIENT	Q-SCORE	DS	P-value (cancer vs normal)
Breast cancer	110	23	0.291	0.668	1.424E-07
Normal	12	5	4.583	1.311	
Carcinoids cancer	38	6	0.368	0.942	7.619E-01
Normal	14	7	0.290	0.611	
Cervical cancer	103	25	4.932	2.847	2.400E-04
Normal	14	7	6.000	0.000	
Colorectal cancer	112	29	1.098	1.719	2.337E-02
Normal	14	8	0.429	0.852	
Endometrial cancer	108	24	4.009	2.628	2.741E-01
Normal	15	7	4.800	2.484	
Glioma	106	25	1.132	1.696	8.000E-06
Normal	15	9	0.200	0.414	
Head and neck cancer	35	9	4.543	3.293	4.676E-07
Normal	14	8	8.360	1.277	
Liver cancer	108	24	1.694	2.921	2.733E-03
Normal	15	5	0.600	0.828	
Lung	106	27	1.821	1.178	4.413E-03
Normal	15	6	2.800	1.521	
Lymphoma	109	22	0.110	0.458	5.514E-01
Normal	10	5	0.200	0.422	
Melanoma	105	23	4.000	3.290	3.331E-03
Normal	15	9	5.400	1.242	
Ovarian cancer	108	19	4.148	2.445	7.246E-06
Normal	14	7	1.000	1.519	
Pancreatic cancer	96	35	4.354	3.296	8.336E-21
Normal	14	7	0.210	0.426	
Prostate cancer	98	32	1.735	1.756	1.617E-30
Normal	15	7	9.000	0.000	
Renal cancer	112	22	3.152	2.854	1.226E-06
Normal	15	7	0.800	1.207	
Skin cancer	101	28	4.713	3.539	2.702E-05
Normal	15	9	7.200	1.521	
Stomach cancer	95	20	1.874	2.515	4.525E-04
Normal	11	5	1.090	2.427	
Testis cancer	105	28	0.257	0.772	3.236E-03
Normal	12	7	0.500	1.168	
Thyroid cancer	38	7	6.947	3.579	1.007E-07
Normal	14	6	2.429	1.604	
Urothelial cancer	111	27	4.505	2.957	9.705E-08
Normal	10	6	6.900	1.449	

Supplementary Table 2: Q-score (non-significant) average and standard deviation analyzed for 20 types of cancerous samples.

SAMPLE	Q-SCORE	P-value (cancer vs normal)
Carcinoids	0.368	7.6189E-01
Normal	0.290	
Endometrial cancer	4.009	2.7406E-01
Normal	4.800	
Lymphoma	0.110	5.5144E-01
Normal	0.200	

Supplementary Table 3: Q-score (up-regulation) average and standard deviation analyzed for 20 types of cancerous samples.

SAMPLE	Q-SCORE	P-value (cancer vs normal)
Pancreatic cancer	4.354	8.3359E-21
Normal	0.210	
Thyroid cancer	6.947	1.0071E-07
Normal	2.429	
Renal cancer	3.152	1.2257E-06
Normal	0.800	
Ovarian cancer	4.148	7.2464E-06
Normal	1.000	
Glioma	1.132	8.0000E-06
Normal	0.200	
Stomach cancer	1.874	4.5249E-04
Normal	1.090	
Liver cancer	1.694	2.7334E-03
Normal	0.600	
Lung cancer	1.821	4.4129E-03
Normal	2.800	
Colorectal cancer	1.098	2.3371E-02
Normal	0.429	

Supplementary Table 4: Q-score (down-regulation) average and standard deviation analyzed for 20 types of cancerous samples.

SAMPLE	Q-SCORE	P-value (cancer vs normal)
Prostate cancer	1.735	1.6165E-30
Normal	9.000	
Skin cancer	4.713	2.7017E-05
Normal	7.200	
Urothelial cancer	4.505	9.7046E-08
Normal	6.900	
Breast cancer	0.291	1.4237E-07
Normal	4.583	
Head and Neck cancer	4.543	4.6756E-07
Normal	8.360	
Cervical cancer	4.932	2.4000E-04
Normal	6.000	
Testis cancer	0.257	3.2361E-03
Normal	0.500	
Melanoma	4.000	3.3307E-03
Normal	5.400	

Supplementary Table 5: Number of tissue samples for the assessment of the specificity of antibodies binding to ANXA1 protein in 20 types of cancer.

ANTIBODY NAME	NORMAL SAMPLE	CANCER SAMPLE
HPA011271	55	394
HPA011272	55	394
CAB013023	53	371
CAB035987	56	382
CAB058693	54	363
Total	273	1904

Supplementary Table 6: ANXA1 protein expression according to staining intensity and antibody specificity in cancer samples.

SAMPLE	HPA011271	HPA011272	CAB035987	CAB058693	CAB013023	ANTIBODY STAINING ACCUMULATED
Lymphoma	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.08
Breast	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.15	0.26	0.51
Testis	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.64	0.64
Carcinoids	0.00	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.50	1.00
Colorectal	0.00	0.00	0.27	0.52	1.57	2.36
Glioma	0.29	0.48	0.17	0.90	1.10	2.94
Liver	0.61	0.52	0.19	0.43	1.50	3.26
Stomach	0.44	0.44	0.70	0.44	1.78	3.81
Prostate	0.57	0.27	0.81	0.81	1.44	3.91
Renal	0.83	0.73	1.14	0.70	2.25	5.65
Melanoma	1.24	1.36	1.55	1.05	2.19	7.39
Pancreatic	1.33	1.50	1.50	1.30	2.22	7.86
Lung	1.43	1.65	1.55	1.32	1.95	7.90
Skin	1.38	1.55	1.00	2.22	2.05	8.20
Head and Neck	1.43	1.00	2.17	2.00	2.29	8.88
Ovarian	1.17	1.08	2.24	2.35	2.06	8.90
Urothelial	1.45	1.50	1.79	1.92	2.45	9.12
Endometrial	1.43	1.18	2.17	1.70	2.81	9.29
Cervical	1.68	1.59	2.14	2.24	2.43	10.08
Thyroid	2.25	2.25	2.00	2.50	2.75	11.75
Antibody Staining Accumulated	17.54	17.61	21.55	22.56	34.24	

Scale code:

EXPRESSION	ANTIBODY STAINING	ANTIBODY STAINING
Non-Detected	0	0
Low	0,01-1,00	0,01-1,00
Medium	1,01-2,00	1,01-2,00
High	2,01-3,00	2,01-3,00

Supplementary Table 7: ANXA1 protein expression according to staining intensity and antibody specificity in normal samples.

NORMAL SAMPLE	HPA011272	HPA011271	CAB035987	CAB058693	CAB013023	ANTIBODY STAINING ACCUMULATED
Pancreas Normal	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Glioma Normal	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Lymphoma Normal	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Carcinoids_Normal	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.33	0.33
Cervical_Normal	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.33	0.33
Colorectal_Normal	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00
Liver Normal	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00
Testis Normal	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00
Renal Normal	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.00	2.00
Stomach Normal	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.00	2.00
Ovarian Normal	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.00	1.00	3.00
Prostate Normal	0.27	0.57	0.81	0.81	1.44	3.91
Thyroid Normal	0.00	1.00	1.00	2.00	2.00	6.00
Lung Normal	0.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	8.00
Melanoma Normal	3.00	2.00	2.00	1.00	2.00	10.00
Normal_Breast	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	11.00
Endometrium Normal	2.00	2.00	2.67	3.00	2.00	11.67
Skin Normal	2.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	12.00
Urothelial Normal	2.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	12.00
Head and Neck Normal	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	15.00
Antibody Staining Accumulated	14.27	16.57	19.48	20.81	29.11	

Supplementary Table 8: ANXA1 protein expression according to staining intensity and subcellular location in cancer samples.

TYPE	SUBCELLULAR LOCATION	Q-SCORE	N
Breast cancer	Cytoplasmic membranous	1.53	17
	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	1.50	4
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	4.11	9
	Cytoplasmic membranous	6.00	3
Carcinoids	Cytoplasmic/membranous	2.33	6
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	2.00	1
	Cytoplasmic membranous	1.00	2
Cervical cancer	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	5.98	64
	Cytoplasmic membranous	4.31	29
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	6.00	9
	Cytoplasmic membranous	6.00	5
Colorectal cancer	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	3.00	16
	Cytoplasmic membranous	2.59	29
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous	2.00	3
Endometrial cancer	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	5.25	61
	Cytoplasmic membranous	3.42	33
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	5.25	12
	Cytoplasmic membranous	3.00	3
Glioma	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	4.14	14
	Cytoplasmic membranous	2.14	28
	Nuclear	2.00	1
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous	1.00	3
Head and Neck cancer	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	6.71	17
	Cytoplasmic membranous	4.09	11
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	8.36	14
Liver cancer	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	7.06	18
	Cytoplasmic membranous	3.11	18
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous	1.50	6
Lung cancer	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	2.50	22
	Cytoplasmic membranous	2.16	61
	Nuclear	2.00	3
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	4.00	6
	Cytoplasmic membranous	3.00	3
Lymphoma	Cytoplasmic/membranous	1.33	9
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous	1.00	2
Melanoma	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	6.44	27
	Cytoplasmic membranous	4.88	48
	Nuclear	6.00	2
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	3.00	3
	Cytoplasmic membranous	6.00	9
	Nuclear	6.00	3
Ovarian cancer	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	5.03	59
	Cytoplasmic membranous	3.51	43
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	4.00	2
	Cytoplasmic membranous	2.00	3
Pancreatic cancer	Cytoplasmic/membranous, nuclear	6.87	39

	Cytoplasmic membranous	4.55	33
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous	1.00	3
Prostate cancer	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	3.29	14
	Cytoplasmic membranous	2.61	46
	Nuclear	2.00	2
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	9.00	9
	Cytoplasmic membranous	9.00	6
Renal cancer	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	6.25	24
	Cytoplasmic membranous	3.39	56
	Nuclear	2.60	5
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	3.00	3
	Cytoplasmic membranous	1.00	3
Skin cancer	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	7.00	39
	Cytoplasmic membranous	5.57	35
	Nuclear	2.67	3
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	7.50	12
	Cytoplasmic membranous	6.00	3
Stomach cancer	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	4.11	19
	Cytoplasmic membranous	3.06	32
	Nuclear	1.00	2
Normal	Cytoplasmic/membranous	6.00	2
Testis cancer	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	2.00	2
	Cytoplasmic membranous	2.56	9
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous	3.00	2
Thyroid cancer	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	8.14	28
	Cytoplasmic membranous	9.00	4
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	3.50	8
	Cytoplasmic membranous	2.00	3
Urothelial cancer	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	6.54	35
	Cytoplasmic membranous	4.54	57
	Nuclear	2.00	6
Normal	Cytoplasmic membranous, nuclear	7.50	6
	Cytoplasmic membranous	6.00	4

Supplementary Table 9: ANXA1 protein expression according to staining intensity and subcellular location in cancer and normal samples.

SUBCELLULAR LOCATION	CANCER		NORMAL	
	Q-SCORE	N (%)	Q-SCORE	N (%)
Cytoplasmic/membranous	3.50	604 (53,5%)	5.79	94 (57,0%)
Cytoplasmic/membranous, nuclear	5.69	502 (44,4%)	4.03	68(41,2%)
Nuclear	2.46	24 (2,1%)	6.00	3 (1,8%)
Total		1130 (100%)		165 (100%)

Supplementary Figure 1: Venn diagram of ANXA1 protein expression according to subcellular location in cancer samples.

Supplementary Figure 2: Venn diagram of ANXA1 protein expression according to subcellular location in normal tissue samples.

